

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

LINSEED OIL: EXTRACTION, HEALTH ADVANTAGES AND MAIN INGREDIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Flaxseed (linseed oil) is rich in α -linolenic acid (ALA), lignans, proteins, and dietary fibers, which have been considered an essential food ingredient. Besides mechanical pressing and solvent extraction for flaxseed oil, various new extraction processes, for example, microwave-assisted extraction, supercritical CO₂ extraction, subcritical extraction, three-phase partitioning, enzyme-assisted three-phase partitioning, etc., have been investigated. However, due to the high ALA in flaxseed oil, it is a great challenge for the development of flaxseed oil-based products. In the present paper, the latest developments in the extraction of flaxseed oil, the potential benefits of flaxseed oil, and flaxseed oil-based foods were reviewed.

Keywords: linseed oil, α -linolenic acid, natural compounds, extraction method, chemical composition.

Introduction

Linseed is one of the oldest oilseeds and is grown in more than 50 countries. The meaning of flaxseed in Latin is "very useful". Currently, the main areas of flaxseed cultivation are located in the northern hemisphere, including Canada, Mainland China, America, India, and Ethiopia. Among these countries are Canada and mainland China is the largest exporter, accounting for more than 30% of the flaxseed trade (6).

Flaxseed contains many bioactive compounds including ALA, lignin, protein, mucilage, minerals, and

phenolic compounds, which can provide potential benefits to our body, such as reducing the probability of occurrence of heart diseases, and osteoporosis, anti-mammary or prostate gland tumor activities, laxative activity, anti-inflammatory activity, and alleviating menopausal symptoms, etc (1,2).

The amount of these components in flaxseed strongly depends on many factors, such as flaxseed varieties, harvest time, growing conditions, processing, analysis methods, etc. (3, 4). Flaxseed is one of the richest sources of phytoestrogens.

Table 1.

Fatty acid profiles of whole flaxseed and flaxseed oil.

Fatty acids	Whole flaxseed			(%) Flaxseed oil (%)	
Palmitic acid	5.96–7.18 ^a	5.76–6.63 ^b	5.67–6.34 ^c	5.13 ^d	4.66 ^e
Stearic acid	4.38–5.33 ^a	4.13–5.63 ^b	4.28–6.35 ^c	3.38 ^d	4.43 ^e
Oleic acid	18.51–31.19 ^a	26.38–31.38 ^b	22.41–31.13 ^c	19.3 ^d	18.5 ^e
Linoleic acid	12.03–16.52 ^a	13.85–14.91 ^b	12.45–15.37 ^c	14.0 ^d	14.5 ^e
Linolenic acid	42.67–58.51 ^a	43.54–48.35 ^b	45.09–51.09 ^c	55.4 ^d	55.8 ^e

Linseed oil also contains many types of phenolic compounds, for example, syringic acid, ferulic acid, cinnamic acid, gallic acid, etc. Deng et al. (4) found that the total number of phenolic compounds ranged from 109.93 to 246.88 mg GAE/100 g (Table 1).

Materials and methods

Currently, the most common methods of extracting linseed oil are mechanical pressing and solvent extraction. Fresh unrefined oil from pressed flaxseed has a nutty taste, and the color varies from yellow to orange. Like other edible oils on the market, it needs to be purified through the process of settling, alkaline purification, dehumidification, bleaching, insulation, and deodorization. Sometimes homemade cold-pressed oils can be used directly for cooking without further refining. The extraction of linseed oil can be influenced by several factors, such as the pretreatment of linseed, the moisture content of linseed, varieties, pressing conditions, etc. (5,10,11).

Although the mechanical pressing method is quite popular for processing linseed oil, the disadvantage of this method is the low degree of oil extraction. To increase the yield of the extracted oil, many new extraction methods have been developed, for example, ultrasound extraction, microwave extraction, supercritical CO₂ extraction, subcritical extraction, three-phase separation, three-phase separation using enzymes, etc. (7,8).

Results and discussions

Flaxseed has been used as a dietary supplement in our daily lives for many years. Whole or crushed flaxseeds are convenient to use as additives to the dough, batters, and various bakery products. In addition, flaxseed flour can be used as a substitute for wheat flour or eggs, especially in some bakery products, such as bread, cupcakes, cookies, etc. Being one of the main components of flaxseed, flaxseed oil is gaining popularity due to its high alcohol content (Table 2).

Table 2.

Applications of flaxseed oil in foods.

Food types	Additions	References
Alaska pollock surimi	10% oil (flaxseed: algae: menhaden, 8: 1:1)	Debusca et al. (2013)
Cheese	1.0% flaxseed oil	Aguirre and Canovas (2012)
Shortening & cookies	0–50% flaxseed oil	Rangrej et al. (2015)
Bread	1.0, 2.5, 5.0 and 10% flaxseed oil (powder)	Gokmen et al. (2011)
Ice cream	4.0% flaxseed oil powder	Gowda et al. (2018)
Milk	4.0% flaxseed oil	Tang et al. (2016a, 2016b, 2016c, 2016d)
Solid drink powder	50% flaxseed oil	Tang and Bian (2018c, 2018d)
Yogurts	2.0% flaxseed oil 2.0% flaxseed oil plus flaxseed flour 1.0%	Tang (2019a, 2019b) Kumar et al. (2017)

Many studies have investigated the potential applications of flaxseed oil in various bakery products. Although most of the studies are focused on the laboratory scale, the results indicate bakery products may be ideal formations for the applications of flaxseed oil due to the huge consumption of bakery products.

As is well known, one particular oil can not satisfy all the nutritional requirements. Therefore, in order to satisfy commercial requirements, oils need to be modified. Among modification methods for oils, blending oils may be one of the simplest methods to modify fatty acid profile, and physicochemical and nutritional properties which can meet the requirements of industrial applications.

Conclusion

Among the bioactives in flaxseed, research scientists and consumers are interested in flaxseed oil, particularly ALA in flaxseed oil. At present, flaxseed oil-based products have been available. Though we've made some achievements, more investigations should be carried out in the future. Firstly, many consumers do not sufficiently realize the potential advantages of flaxseed oil for our health. Therefore, we need to improve the cognitive ability of flaxseed oil in the future. Secondly, the high-value-added flaxseed oil-based products are still limited and should be developed.

Thirdly, because of the poor stability of ALA in flaxseed oil, the application of flaxseed oil in the food industry still is facing a great challenge. In order to minimize oil oxidation, many advanced techniques, for example, the production technology of nano-emulsion (micro-fluidization, microwave, high power ultrasound, etc.), spray drying, etc., should be attempted to protect flaxseed oil, and will further expand the utilization of flaxseed oil. In addition, although more evidence has indicated flaxseed oil has health-promoting benefits, many more studies need to be carried out to resolve the results regarding the mechanisms of flaxseed oil for disease treatment. Furthermore, the production of ALA-enriched animal-origin products by feeding a flaxseed oil-enriched diet should be developed further.

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